

Thank you for your interest in this survey. This study is conducted by the Department of Artificial Intelligence and Human Interfaces at the University of Salzburg and will take approximately 10–15 minutes to complete.

Section A: Welcome

Thank you for your interest in this survey. This study is conducted by the Department of Artificial Intelligence and Human Interfaces at the University of Salzburg and will take approximately 20 minutes to complete.

The goal of this research is to explore how drivers perceive data transparency in the context of Vehicular Digital Twins (VDTs) - digital representations of vehicles that continuously collect, process, and mirror real-time driving data. These systems are increasingly used for purposes such as predictive maintenance, personalization, and safety improvements.

With this survey, we aim to better understand:

What drivers know or assume about the types of data their vehicle collects. What level of transparency they expect regarding data collection, usage, and sharing. How much control they desire over their personal and vehicle-related data.

Your responses will help us inform the design of user-centered, privacy-aware interfaces in future vehicle systems. We greatly appreciate your participation.

Section B: Consent Form

B1. Please read the following information carefully before deciding whether or not to participate in this survey.

It is important that you understand the purpose of the study, what your involvement will entail, and the potential risks and benefits associated with your participation. The following information should provide an overview of what your participation requires.

ProceduresIf you agree to participate, you will be asked to complete a survey that should take approximately 20-25 minutes.

BenefitsWhile there is no direct benefit to you for participating, your feedback is valuable in advancing research in human-computer interaction and innovative driving safety technologies. Your participation will contribute to a broader understanding of driver behavior and technology acceptance.

Voluntary Participation and WithdrawalYour participation in this survey is entirely voluntary. You may choose not to answer any question that makes you feel uncomfortable and you may withdraw from the survey at any time without penalty or loss of benefits. Close your browser if you wish to discontinue your participation.

Confidentiality and Data ProtectionData from all participants will be aggregated and anonymized to ensure that individual participants cannot be identified. All data will be securely stored and accessible only to the research team. The information collected will be used solely for research purposes and may be published in academic venues in a manner that does not reveal your identity. All data will be securely retained until the completion of the doctoral thesis of the main researcher to ensure proper analysis and reporting.

Contact InformationIf you have any questions or concerns regarding this research study, please feel free to contact Cansu Demir (cansu.demir@plus.ac.at), Doctoral Candidate in Digital and Analytical Sciences at the University of Salzburg.

Consent StatementBy proceeding with and completing this survey, you acknowledge that: You have read and understood the information provided above. You are at least 18 years old and voluntarily agree to participate in this research study. You understand that you may withdraw your consent and discontinue participation at any time without any negative consequences. If you agree to the terms outlined above, please indicate your consent by selecting the “Agree” option

Section C: Missing Consent

Your informed consent is required for participating in this survey. You can now close this window.

Section D: Background Information

D1. Do you currently hold a valid driver's license?

Yes

No

D2. How many years have you held your driver's license?

Less than 1 year

1-5 years

6-10 years

11-20 years

21-30 years

More than 30 years

D3. How often do you drive?

Daily

A few times per week

Occasionally

Rarely

Never

D4. What kind of vehicle do you mostly drive?

Traditional vehicle (no or minimal digital systems, e.g., analog radio, no connectivity)

Digitally enhanced vehicle (basic digital features like Bluetooth, basic infotainment, cruise control)

Connected vehicle (internet-connected, real-time navigation, software updates, remote diagnostics)

Electric or hybrid vehicle (with advanced connectivity and energy monitoring features)

Rental/shared mobility vehicle (e.g., car-sharing, ride-hailing, subscription models)

Other

Other

Section E: Missing License

A valid driver's license is required to participate in this survey. You can close this window now.

Section F: Vehicle Features

Have you at any time used the following features in a vehicle?

F1. Safety & Monitoring Systems

Emergency call functionality

Dashcam or driving event recorder

Forward collision warning or automatic braking

Blind spot monitoring

Over-the-air software updates

None of the above

F2. Comfort & Convenience Features

Adaptive suspension

Customizable ambient lighting

Heated or ventilated seats

Gesture control for infotainment system

Digital vehicle key or smart keycard

None of the above

F3. Navigation & Driving Assistance

Real-time traffic information

Adaptive cruise control

Lane keeping assistance

Automated parking assistance (including reversing assistant)

Driving behavior feedback

Head-up display

Night vision assist

None of the above

F4. Charging & Electric Vehicle Features

Public charging station locator

Charging status monitoring via app

Remote pre-conditioning (heating or cooling)

Dedicated electric drive mode or services

None of the above

F5. In-Car Connectivity & Entertainment

Smartphone integration (e.g., Apple CarPlay or Android Auto)

Voice-activated digital assistant

In-car gaming or media streaming services

Personalized driver profiles/settings

Integration with third-party apps (e.g., music or audiobook services)

Use of digital store to activate additional features

None of the above

F6. Remote & Mobile App Features

Remote engine start

Remote lock/unlock via smartphone app

Vehicle location tracking via mobile app

Sending destinations to vehicle via mobile app

None of the above

Section G: Understanding of Vehicle Data Collection

G1. Assume that the following features are collecting data about your vehicle and your driving behaviour. Who do you think might have access to this data?

Select all that apply

Navigation & Driving Assistance

Myself

Family members (who also drive)

- Vehicle manufacturer
- Authorized repair shops
- Insurance providers
- Law enforcement
- Third-party service providers
- Not sure
- Other

G2. Assume that the following features are collecting data about your vehicle and your driving behaviour. Who do you think might have access to this data?

Select all that apply

Remote & Mobile App Features

- Myself
- Family members (who also drive)
- Vehicle manufacturer
- Authorized repair shops
- Insurance providers
- Law enforcement
- Third-party service providers
- Not sure
- Other

G3. Assume that the following features are collecting data about your vehicle and your driving behaviour. Who do you think might have access to this data?

Select all that apply

In-Car Connectivity & Entertainment

- Myself
- Family members (who also drive)
- Vehicle manufacturer
- Authorized repair shops
- Insurance providers

Law enforcement

Third-party service providers

Not sure

Other

G4. Assume that the following features are collecting data about your vehicle and your driving behaviour. Who do you think might have access to this data?

Select all that apply

Safety & Monitoring Systems

Myself

Family members (who also drive)

Vehicle manufacturer

Authorized repair shops

Insurance providers

Law enforcement

Third-party service providers

Not sure

Other

G5. Assume that the following features are collecting data about your vehicle and your driving behaviour. Who do you think might have access to this data?

Select all that apply

Comfort & Convenience Features

Myself

Family members (who also drive)

Vehicle manufacturer

Authorized repair shops

Insurance providers

Law enforcement

Third-party service providers

Not sure

Other

G6. Assume that the following features are collecting data about your vehicle and your driving behaviour. Who do you think might have access to this data?

Select all that apply

Charging & Electric Vehicle Features

- Myself
- Family members (who also drive)
- Vehicle manufacturer
- Authorized repair shops
- Insurance providers
- Law enforcement
- Third-party service providers
- Not sure
- Other

G7. Assume that the following features are collecting data about your vehicle and your driving behaviour. Who do you think might have access to this data?

Select all that apply

Software Updates or Feature Activations

- Myself
- Family members (who also drive)
- Vehicle manufacturer
- Authorized repair shops
- Insurance providers
- Law enforcement
- Third-party service providers
- Not sure
- Other

G8. If you at any point selected the "other" option, please write in 1-2 sentences who you think has access to the data:

G9. How confident are you that you understand who can see or use the data your vehicle collects?

- Extremely confident
- Very confident
- Confident
- Neutral
- Not confident
- Not very confident
- Not at all confident

G10. How confident are you that you understand what kinds of data your vehicle collects?

- Extremely confident
- Very confident
- Confident
- Neutral
- Not confident
- Not very confident
- Not at all confident

Section H: Vehicular Digital Twin

A Vehicular Digital Twin (VDT) is a virtual model of a real-world vehicle. It collects and processes real-time data (such as speed, location, driving behavior, and technical diagnostics) to mirror the condition and performance of the actual vehicle. VDTs are commonly used for predictive maintenance, system optimization, personalization, and advanced safety features.

Please read the following scenario carefully: *You are driving to another city. As you drive, your car continuously sends data like how hard you brake, your route, and engine status to its digital twin stored in the cloud. The VDT personalizes your driving experience by suggesting preferred routes based on past trips. Later, the VDT detects abnormal brake wear and automatically shares this information with your chosen repair shop. You then receive a notification suggesting a maintenance appointment before any problems occur.*

Please answer the following questions considering this scenario before clicking "next" at the bottom of the page.

H1. Is this the first time you have heard about the concept of a "digital twin" in vehicles?

Yes, this is the first time

I've heard of it, but I don't know much about it

I'm somewhat familiar with the concept

I'm very familiar with the concept

H2. How comfortable are you with the idea of a vehicle creating a digital twin to support maintenance?

Not at all comfortable

Slightly comfortable

Somewhat comfortable

Neutral

Moderately comfortable

Very comfortable

Extremely comfortable

H3. How comfortable are you with the idea of a vehicle creating a digital twin to support safety?

- Not at all comfortable
- Slightly comfortable
- Somewhat comfortable
- Neutral
- Moderately comfortable
- Very comfortable
- Extremely comfortable

H4. How comfortable are you with the idea of a vehicle creating a digital twin to support personalization?

- Not at all comfortable
- Slightly comfortable
- Somewhat comfortable
- Neutral
- Moderately comfortable
- Very comfortable
- Extremely comfortable

H5. Would you want to be informed when a vehicular digital twin starts collecting new types of data?

- Yes, always
- Only if personal or sensitive data is involved
- Only if I can opt out
- No, I don't need to be informed
- Other

Other

H6. What kind of data do you consider sensitive in the context of a vehicle's digital twin?

H7. What concerns, if any, do you have about the use of vehicular digital twins?

Section I: Control and Transparency

I1. How important is it for you to have control over what data is collected from your vehicle?

- Extremely important
- Very important
- Moderately important
- Neutral
- Somewhat important
- Slightly important
- Not at all important

I2. Which features would you like to have in a data transparency dashboard in a vehicle?

- Overview of what data is being collected
- Real-time view of data being shared
- History/log of data access or sharing events
- Visualization of where data is going (e.g., manufacturer, third parties)
- Explanations for why specific data is collected
- Alerts when new data types start being collected

I do not need any of these features

Other

Other

I3. Which control features would you like to have regarding your vehicle's data collection?

Ability to turn data collection on or off entirely

Ability to pause or delay data collection temporarily

Ability to choose which types of data are collected

Ability to anonymize/pseudonymize data before sharing

Ability to delete data previously collected

I do not need any control features

Other

Other

I4. When should you be notified about the following types of data sharing?

Navigation & driving assistance

In real-time

Daily summary

Only on request

Never

I5. When should you be notified about the following types of data sharing?

Remote & mobile app functions

In real-time

Daily summary

Only on request

Never

**I6. When should you be notified about the following types of data sharing?
In-car entertainment & personalization**

- In real-time
- Daily summary
- Only on request
- Never

**I7. When should you be notified about the following types of data sharing?
Safety & monitoring systems**

- In real-time
- Daily summary
- Only on request
- Never

**I8. When should you be notified about the following types of data sharing?
Comfort & convenience settings**

- In real-time
- Daily summary
- Only on request
- Never

**I9. When should you be notified about the following types of data sharing?
Charging & electric vehicle features**

- In real-time
- Daily summary
- Only on request
- Never

**I10. When should you be notified about the following types of data sharing?
Software updates or feature activations**

- In real-time
- Daily summary
- Only on request
- Never

**I11. When should you be notified about the following types of data sharing?
Location, driving behavior, or journey data**

- In real-time
- Daily summary
- Only on request
- Never

**I12. When should you be notified about the following types of data sharing?
Audio/video recording inside the cabin**

- In real-time
- Daily summary
- Only on request
- Never

**I13. When should you be notified about the following types of data sharing?
Sharing with third parties (e.g., insurers)**

- In real-time
- Daily summary
- Only on request
- Never

**I14. How would you prefer these notifications to be delivered?
Navigation & driving assistance**

- In-App message
- Dashboard display
- Both
- Other
- None

**I15. How would you prefer these notifications to be delivered?
Remote & mobile app functions**

- In-App message
- Dashboard display
- Both
- Other

None

**I16. How would you prefer these notifications to be delivered?
In-car entertainment & personalization**

In-App message

Dashboard display

Both

Other

None

**I17. How would you prefer these notifications to be delivered?
Safety & monitoring systems**

In-App message

Dashboard display

Both

Other

None

**I18. How would you prefer these notifications to be delivered?
Comfort & convenience settings**

In-App message

Dashboard display

Both

Other

None

**I19. How would you prefer these notifications to be delivered?
Charging & electric vehicle features**

In-App message

Dashboard display

Both

Other

None

**I20. How would you prefer these notifications to be delivered?
Software updates or feature activations**

In-App message

Dashboard display

Both

Other

None

**I21. How would you prefer these notifications to be delivered?
Location, driving behavior, or journey data**

In-App message

Dashboard display

Both

Other

None

**I22. How would you prefer these notifications to be delivered?
Audio/video recording inside the cabin**

In-App message

Dashboard display

Both

Other

None

**I23. How would you prefer these notifications to be delivered?
Sharing with third parties (e.g., insurers)**

In-App message

Dashboard display

Both

Other

None

**I24. If a vehicle (or your vehicle) asked for your consent before sharing
data, what would be your preferred approach?**

Ask me every time

Ask once per trip

Ask once and remember my choice

Only ask if something changes

I do not need to be asked

I25. In shared vehicles, I want my personal data (e.g., routes, preferences) to remain private from other drivers.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Slightly disagree
- Neutral
- Slightly agree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

I26. In rental vehicles, I want my personal data (e.g., routes, preferences) to remain private from the provider.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Slightly disagree
- Neutral
- Slightly agree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

I27. I would share more data if it resulted in personal benefits (e.g., lower insurance, faster repairs).

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Slightly disagree
- Neutral
- Slightly agree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

I28. Rank the following features from most important (1) to least important (5):

- Transparency of data collection
- Control over data sharing
- Trust in the system

1 Strongly disagree 2 3 4 Neither disagree nor agree 5 6 7 Strongly agree N/A

All things considered, the vehicular digital twin would cause serious privacy problems.

Compared to others, I am more sensitive about the way automotive companies handle my personal information.

To me, it is the most important thing to keep my privacy intact from automotive companies.

I believe other people are too much concerned with driver privacy issues.

Compared with other subjects on my mind, personal privacy is very important.

I am concerned about threats to my personal privacy today.

Section K: Demographics

K1. In which age group do you belong?

- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65+

K2. Which gender do you identify with?

Female

Male

Non-binary

Prefer not to say

Self Describe:

Self Describe:

K3. What is you country of residence?

K4. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

No formal education

Primary education

Secondary education (e.g., high school, diploma)

Vocational or technical training

Bachelor's degree or equivalent

Master's degree or equivalent

Doctorate or PhD

Prefer not to say

Other

Other

K5. Do you live in a:

Urban area

Suburban area

Rural area

K6. How privacy-aware do you consider yourself?

Extremely privacy-aware

Very privacy-aware

Modaerately privacy-aware

Neutral

Slightly privacy-aware

Minimally privacy-aware

Not at all privacy-aware

Section L: Final Screen

L1.

Thank you for your participation! Your insights help us understand user expectations for transparency and control in vehicular digital twins.

If you would like to receive study results or be contacted for a follow-up driving simulator study, please leave your email.

If you choose to provide your email, this information will be stored separately from your survey responses and it will be used only for the stated purposes.